

UNLOCKING THE SECRETS TO TEACHING ACADEMIC WRITING ACROSS DIFFERENT GENRES

Sayfiddinov I.

Master's Degree Student in English Linguistics, an English instructor at Turan International
University, Namangan, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This study explores the intricacies of teaching academic writing across various genres, emphasizing the alignment of pedagogical approaches with specific writing types. Academic writing, a critical skill for academic success and professional communication, encompasses a wide range of genres, each requiring unique conventions and structures. The research analyzes genres such as essays, research papers, theses, reports, and proposals, linking them to instructional strategies such as process-based, genre-based, and task-based approaches. By synthesizing theoretical models and practical applications, the study proposes a comprehensive framework to guide educators in developing students' writing proficiency. The findings highlight the importance of tailored teaching methods, including scaffolding, reflective practice, and technology-enhanced instruction, in addressing the diverse challenges of academic writing. This study underscores the role of academic writing in preparing students for both academic and professional success, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application.*

Keywords: *academic writing, teaching methods, process-based approach, genre-based approach, task-based learning, academic genres, writing instruction.*

Introduction

The diverse demands of academic writing necessitate an understanding of various genres, each with its unique conventions, purposes, and structures. Whether writing essays, research papers, theses, or reports, students and professionals must adapt their writing strategies to meet the expectations of these forms. Academic writing is not only a critical skill for academic success but also a foundational tool for effective communication in professional settings. Essays, for instance, serve as a medium for analysis, argumentation, and explanation, while research papers and theses provide a platform for presenting original findings and exploring theories (Hyland, 2006). Reports, annotated bibliographies, and policy briefs cater to more practical applications, such as documenting experiments, synthesizing research, or influencing decision-making (Biber et al., 2002; Pecorari, 2013).

Teaching these genres effectively requires tailored instructional approaches. Pedagogical strategies, such as the process-based, genre-based, and task-based approaches, play a crucial role in equipping students with the skills to navigate the complexities of academic writing (Swales & Feak, 2012). For example, process-based approaches emphasize iterative improvement, guiding students through drafting and revision stages, while genre-based methods focus on the structural and stylistic conventions of specific texts (Badger & White, 2000). Task-based learning, on the other hand, connects academic writing tasks to real-world contexts, enhancing relevance and engagement (Pecorari, 2013).

This article examines the best practices for teaching academic writing across different genres, emphasizing the alignment between writing types and instructional approaches. By analyzing various methods, such as scaffolding, reflective practice, and technology-enhanced

instruction, this study aims to provide educators with a comprehensive framework for developing students' writing proficiency. The discussion highlights the importance of adapting pedagogical strategies to the unique requirements of each genre, ensuring that learners are well-prepared for both academic and professional challenges.

Methodology

To explore the optimal instructional approaches for teaching academic writing, this study employed a qualitative analysis of pedagogical frameworks and their application across various genres of writing. A comprehensive review of existing literature was conducted, drawing from key academic works such as Hyland (2006), Swales and Feak (2012), and Murray and Moore (2006). These sources provided insights into the theoretical underpinnings of process-based, genre-based, and task-based approaches, as well as other methods like scaffolding, explicit instruction, and reflective practice.

The research also included an in-depth examination of academic writing types, including essays, research papers, theses, reports, and proposals, among others. Each genre was analyzed to identify its distinctive features, challenges, and instructional needs. For instance, essays were categorized into descriptive, analytical, argumentative, and expository types, with each subtype linked to a specific pedagogical approach. Similarly, research papers were examined through their subcategories, such as empirical and review papers, to determine the most suitable teaching methods.

To evaluate the effectiveness of these instructional strategies, a framework was developed to align writing genres with pedagogical approaches. This framework integrated theoretical models with practical applications, highlighting the key reasons for selecting particular methods for specific genres. For example, task-based learning was linked to argumentative essays and case studies due to its emphasis on real-world problem-solving and evidence-based argumentation (Willis, 1996). Meanwhile, model text analysis was paired with literature reviews and research proposals to provide learners with concrete examples of academic conventions (Johns, 1997).

Data from classroom practices, case studies, and reflective journals were analyzed to validate the proposed framework. The iterative process of linking writing types to instructional methods ensured that the recommendations were grounded in both theory and practice. The study also considered the role of technology in enhancing writing instruction, incorporating tools such as Grammarly and Turnitin to support error correction and originality (Pajares, 2003).

By synthesizing findings from the literature and practical applications, this methodology offers a robust approach to understanding how tailored instructional strategies can address the diverse requirements of academic writing genres. The results underscore the importance of combining theoretical insights with practical tools to foster students' academic and professional success.

Literature review

Essays encompass various types, each serving distinct purposes. Descriptive essays aim to provide vivid and detailed descriptions of a topic, event, or concept. Analytical essays focus on breaking down a subject into components to gain a deeper understanding. Argumentative essays present well-supported arguments to persuade readers of a specific perspective, while compare and contrast essays examine similarities and differences between two or more subjects. Expository essays are straightforward, aiming to explain topics or concepts clearly and concisely (Hyland, 2006).

Research papers include several categories. Empirical research papers report original findings, detailing methodologies, results, and analyses. Review papers synthesize and evaluate existing research on a particular subject, while theoretical papers delve into or propose theories within specific academic disciplines (Swales & Feak, 2012).

Theses and dissertations are essential research projects. A thesis, usually required for a master's degree, presents research findings on a specific topic, while a dissertation, necessary for a doctoral degree, involves more extensive and original research (Murray & Moore, 2006).

Reports are another critical academic genre. Lab reports document experiments, their methodologies, and results within scientific disciplines. Case studies analyze specific instances or phenomena in depth. Feasibility reports evaluate the practicality of projects or ideas, and field reports record findings and observations from real-world or fieldwork settings (Biber et al., 2002).

Literature reviews critically survey and synthesize existing research on a topic, identifying gaps, trends, and contributions. Annotated bibliographies offer curated lists of sources, summarizing and evaluating their relevance and quality. Abstracts, on the other hand, provide brief summaries of larger academic works such as research papers or theses, enabling readers to grasp the essential content quickly (Pecorari, 2013).

Book and article review critically analyze the contributions of books or journal articles to their respective fields. Proposals, including research proposals and grant proposals, outline objectives, methods, and the significance of planned projects or funding requests, often highlighting their potential impact (Lea & Street, 1998).

Academic articles, published in peer-reviewed journals, present original research, reviews, or theoretical discussions. Conference papers summarize ongoing or completed research and are typically presented at scholarly gatherings. Critical analyses evaluate texts, theories, artworks, or arguments, often assessing their validity and effectiveness. Case studies, meanwhile, focus on real-world problems or phenomena, offering detailed investigations (Russell et al., 2009).

Reflections and personal statements are typically used in applications or self-assessments, blending personal experiences with academic insights. Synthesis papers integrate information from multiple sources to present a new perspective or argument. White papers, authoritative guides often addressing policy or technical issues, aim to provide practical solutions (Bazerman, 2004).

Position papers present and defend a specific stance on an issue, often used in policymaking or debates. Capstone projects serve as culminating academic assignments, integrating knowledge from an entire course of study. Policy briefs, concise and targeted, summarize research findings and their implications for policymakers. Critiques evaluate theories, artworks, or methodologies in detail, while technical writing involves creating manuals, specifications, or instructions in scientific and technical disciplines (Hyland, 2006).

A process-based approach views writing as a step-by-step activity, encompassing stages like brainstorming, drafting, revising, editing, and publishing. It employs techniques such as mind mapping and outlining during pre-writing, peer reviews for feedback, and iterative revision. This approach fosters critical thinking and emphasizes that quality writing is developed over time (Swales & Feak, 2012).

The genre-based approach centers on teaching students the specific conventions, structures, and styles required for different types of academic texts, such as essays, research papers, and reports. It involves analyzing model texts and practicing tone, style, and language appropriate for each genre, helping learners meet diverse academic expectations effectively (Hyland, 2006).

In task-based learning, students engage in authentic writing tasks tied to real-world academic activities, such as drafting research proposals or writing literature reviews. Collaboration on group essays or reports enhances their practical application of skills while increasing engagement by connecting writing to meaningful academic contexts (Pecorari, 2013).

Scaffolding focuses on building students' writing proficiency through gradual, step-by-step guidance. Complex assignments are broken into manageable parts, such as crafting a thesis statement before writing a full essay. Templates and sentence starters provide initial support, gradually enabling students to work independently, which boosts their confidence (Lea & Street, 1998).

The explicit instruction approach directly teaches conventions, grammar, academic style, and citation practices. Activities include grammar-focused lessons, citation workshops (APA, MLA, Chicago styles), and explicit guidance on academic tone and cohesion. It offers clarity regarding academic expectations, reducing confusion and improving writing quality (Biber et al., 2002).

Peer collaboration and review emphasize the value of mutual learning and feedback. Students critique and revise each other's drafts and collaborate on writing tasks through brainstorming and shared efforts. This approach develops critical reading and editing skills while fostering teamwork and mutual improvement (Murray & Moore, 2006).

Content-based instruction ties writing development to specific academic disciplines. Assignments, such as writing lab reports for science or case studies for business, allow students to practice discipline-specific writing styles. This approach makes instruction relevant and contextual, connecting writing skills to learners' academic fields (Bazerman, 2004).

The integrated skills approach combines writing with reading, listening, and speaking to develop holistic language proficiency. Students summarize academic texts, paraphrase information from multiple sources, and write reflections on discussions, reflecting the interconnected nature of academic communication (Nation, 2001).

Model text analysis uses high-quality academic writing samples to guide students. By deconstructing essays, research papers, or reports, students identify structures, organization, and style. Comparing effective and weak examples helps learners understand what constitutes strong academic writing (Hyland, 2006).

In technology-enhanced instruction, digital tools like Grammarly, Turnitin, and Hemingway improve writing skills through error correction and style refinement. Online platforms offer opportunities for interactive learning, plagiarism checking, and participation in virtual writing workshops, fostering independent learning (Pajares, 2003).

Reflective practice encourages students to evaluate their writing progress critically. Activities like maintaining writing journals to document challenges and reflecting on feedback enable learners to identify growth areas and set improvement goals, promoting self-awareness and responsibility (Swales & Feak, 2012).

Problem-based learning engages students in solving real-world issues through written solutions. Tasks such as drafting proposals or argumentative essays on societal debates foster analytical thinking and practical problem-solving, bridging academic skills and real-world applications (Murray & Moore, 2006).

The workshop method provides interactive, hands-on sessions for improving writing. Immediate feedback and group discussions on common challenges create a supportive learning environment that actively involves students in the writing process (Bazerman, 2004).

A flipped classroom approach shifts instruction to homework through video tutorials and maximizes in-class time for collaborative writing and peer feedback. This method allows students to use classroom sessions for active practice, fostering a more dynamic learning experience (Lea & Street, 1998).

The contrastive rhetoric approach addresses the challenges faced by ESL/EFL learners by comparing academic writing norms across cultures. Through activities focused on rhetorical differences in tone, organization, and formality, this approach helps students adapt to new conventions and overcome cultural barriers in writing (Hyland, 2006).

Results

After carefully and thoroughly learning the intricacies and unique features of each writing discourse, the following table is formulated to signify best approaches for any particular writing type. Although each of them requires a well-rounded approach with a mixed array of different methods, one method weighs over another for certain key reasons highlighted below in writing instructions.

Type of Academic Writing	Most Suitable Teaching Method	Reason
Essays	Process-Based Approach	Encourages iterative improvement, helping students understand structure, revise arguments, and refine analytical skills.
- Descriptive Essays	Genre-Based Approach	Highlights conventions of descriptive writing, focusing on vivid language and detailed observation.
- Analytical Essays	Explicit Instruction & Model Text Analysis	Teaches breaking down complex ideas into parts, using examples to illustrate effective analysis and coherence.
-Argumentative Essays	Task-Based Learning	Engages students in real-world issues, promoting critical thinking and evidence-based argumentation.
- Compare and Contrast Essays	Scaffolding	Breaks down the task into clear steps (e.g., brainstorming similarities/differences, thesis crafting), making the process manageable.
- Expository Essays	Explicit Instruction	Focuses on clarity, coherence, and logical explanation, with direct teaching of structural patterns.
Research Papers	Content-Based Instruction	Focuses on discipline-specific formats and conventions, essential for research paper authenticity.

-Empirical Research Papers	Task-Based Learning & Scaffolding	Guides students through designing, conducting, and reporting research systematically.
- Review Papers	Model Text Analysis & Genre-Based Approach	Demonstrates how to synthesize and critique multiple sources effectively.
- Theoretical Papers	Reflective Practice & Content-Based Instruction	Encourages exploring theories while adhering to discipline-specific expectations.
Theses and Dissertations	Process-Based Approach & Reflective Practice	Supports iterative writing with feedback and self-evaluation, essential for long, complex academic projects.
Reports	Explicit Instruction & Task-Based Learning	Teaches formats and conventions, with real-world tasks like writing lab or case reports.
- Lab Reports	Content-Based Instruction	Focuses on technical language and scientific conventions specific to disciplines.
- Case Studies	Task-Based Learning	Involves analyzing real-world examples, promoting critical thinking and structured reporting.
- Feasibility Reports	Task-Based Learning	Prepares students for practical, decision-oriented writing based on data and evidence.
- Field Reports	Integrated Skills Approach	Combines observation, note-taking, and structured reporting skills.
Literature Reviews	Model Text Analysis & Scaffolding	Provides clear examples of structure while guiding students in synthesizing research.
Annotated Bibliographies	Explicit Instruction	Teaches summarizing and evaluating sources systematically, emphasizing relevance and quality.
Abstracts	Explicit Instruction	Focuses on concise, precise writing with clear structure.
Book/Article Reviews	Reflective Practice	Encourages students to engage critically with texts, offering personal insights and academic evaluation.
Proposals	Task-Based Learning & Scaffolding	Helps students practice outlining objectives, significance, and methodologies, breaking down complex projects into clear plans.
- Research Proposals	Genre-Based Approach	Teaches conventions and expectations specific to research communities.

- Grant Proposals	Task-Based Learning	Prepares students to meet funding requirements with clear, persuasive arguments.
Academic Articles	Content-Based Instruction & Model Text Analysis	Focuses on discipline-specific conventions, using published examples to teach high-level academic writing.
Conference Papers	Task-Based Learning	Mirrors real-world academic presentations, teaching concise, engaging writing.
Critical Analyses	Genre-Based Approach	Focuses on conventions of critique, analyzing effectiveness and validity.
Case Studies	Task-Based Learning	Engages students with practical, real-world problem-solving, emphasizing detailed analysis.
Reflections/Personal Statements	Reflective Practice	Encourages students to connect personal experiences with academic goals, improving self-awareness and narrative skills.
Synthesis Papers	Model Text Analysis & Content-Based Instruction	Teaches integrating multiple sources while maintaining a clear argument.
White Papers	Explicit Instruction	Emphasizes structuring arguments with authoritative evidence and logical solutions.
Position Papers	Task-Based Learning	Helps students develop clear stances with evidence, mirroring real-world debates and policymaking.
Capstone Projects	Process-Based Approach	Encourages planning, researching, and revising comprehensive academic projects.
Policy Briefs	Explicit Instruction & Task-Based Learning	Teaches concise, impactful writing with practical implications for policymakers.
Critiques	Reflective Practice & Model Text Analysis	Combines personal engagement with structured evaluation, supported by examples of effective critiques.
Technical Writing	Explicit Instruction & Content-Based Instruction	Teaches technical conventions and discipline-specific standards for clarity and precision.

Discussion

The study of academic writing instruction methods reveals how specific approaches align with the unique requirements of different types of writing, as outlined in the table. By combining

theoretical frameworks and practical applications, effective methods can foster student engagement, comprehension, and skill development. This discussion explores the instructional approaches that best suit various academic writing types, grounded in the cited literature.

Essays

For essays, process-based approaches are pivotal, as they encourage iterative refinement through drafting and feedback, essential for improving argumentation, coherence, and analytical depth (Badger & White, 2000; Silva, 1993). Each subtype of essay benefits from complementary methods. For example, genre-based approaches suit descriptive essays, as they emphasize the conventions of vivid language and sensory detail (Hyland, 2004). Explicit instruction paired with model text analysis is ideal for analytical essays, enabling students to deconstruct complex ideas and synthesize coherent arguments (Johns, 1997). For argumentative essays, task-based learning immerses students in real-world issues, enhancing their critical thinking and evidence-based reasoning (Willis, 1996). Compare and contrast essays require scaffolding to guide students through identifying relationships and structuring comparative analyses step by step (Vygotsky, 1978). Lastly, explicit instruction for expository essays ensures clarity and coherence, critical for explanatory writing (Graham & Perin, 2007).

Research Papers

Research papers demand specialized approaches due to their academic rigor. Content-based instruction integrates language learning with discipline-specific conventions, ensuring authenticity and relevance (Brinton et al., 1989). For empirical research papers, a blend of task-based learning and scaffolding is effective, as these methods guide students through designing, conducting, and reporting research systematically (Weissberg & Buker, 1990). Review papers benefit from model text analysis and genre-based approaches, teaching students to synthesize and critique multiple sources effectively (Swales, 1990). Reflective practice paired with content-based instruction supports theoretical papers, encouraging students to explore theories while adhering to discipline-specific conventions (Schön, 1983).

Theses and Dissertations

The complexity of theses and dissertations necessitates process-based approaches and reflective practice, as iterative writing and self-evaluation are critical for such extensive academic projects (Paltridge & Starfield, 2007). These methods ensure that students develop and refine their arguments while meeting academic standards.

Reports

Reports, being practical and data-driven, benefit from explicit instruction and task-based learning to teach formats, conventions, and real-world applications. Lab reports require content-based instruction to emphasize technical language and scientific conventions (Weissberg & Buker, 1990). Case studies thrive on task-based learning, involving real-world problem-solving and analysis. Feasibility reports align with task-based learning, as they focus on decision-oriented writing based on evidence. For field reports, the integrated skills approach combines observation, note-taking, and structured reporting, fostering comprehensive learning (Ferris & Hedgcock, 2014).

Literature Reviews

Literature reviews require model text analysis and scaffolding, as these methods provide clear structural examples and guide students in synthesizing research (Johns, 1997). These approaches ensure that students can critically analyze and summarize existing studies.

Annotated Bibliographies

The succinct nature of annotated bibliographies is best taught through explicit instruction, focusing on systematic summarization and evaluation of sources (Fink, 2013).

Abstracts

Abstracts benefit from explicit instruction due to their concise and precise nature, emphasizing structure and brevity (Swales & Feak, 2009).

Book and Article Reviews

Reflective practice is well-suited for book and article reviews, as it encourages students to engage critically with texts, providing personal insights and academic evaluation (Schön, 1983).

Proposals

Proposals align with task-based learning and scaffolding, as these methods help students outline objectives, methodologies, and significance while breaking down complex projects into clear plans (Lockhart, 2000).

Academic Articles

For academic articles, content-based instruction and model text analysis are effective, as they focus on discipline-specific conventions and use published examples to illustrate high-level academic writing (Swales, 1990).

Conference Papers

Conference papers benefit from task-based learning, as this mirrors real-world academic presentations, teaching concise, engaging writing (Willis, 1996).

Critical Analyses and Case Studies

For critical analyses, genre-based approaches emphasize the conventions of critique, while case studies thrive on task-based learning, promoting practical, real-world problem-solving (Hyland, 2004; Vygotsky, 1978).

Reflections and Personal Statements

Reflective practice encourages students to connect personal experiences with academic goals, improving self-awareness and narrative skills (Schön, 1983).

Synthesis Papers and White Papers

Synthesis papers combine model text analysis with content-based instruction, while white papers require explicit instruction to emphasize authoritative arguments and logical solutions (Johns, 1997; Brinton et al., 1989).

Position Papers and Capstone Projects

Position papers benefit from task-based learning, promoting clear, evidence-based stances. Capstone projects align with process-based approaches, encouraging planning, researching, and revising (Badger & White, 2000; Willis, 1996).

Policy Briefs

Policy briefs require explicit instruction and task-based learning, teaching concise, impactful writing with practical implications for policymakers (Dunn, 2015).

Critiques and Technical Writing

Critiques combine reflective practice and model text analysis, fostering personal engagement and structured evaluation. Technical writing relies on explicit instruction and content-based instruction to ensure clarity and precision (Brinton et al., 1989).

This analysis underscores the importance of tailoring instructional methods to the specific requirements of each academic writing type. By aligning pedagogical approaches with the unique

features of these texts, educators can better prepare students for the diverse demands of academic and professional communication. The integration of process, content, and task-based strategies ensures both skill development and academic success.

Conclusion

The findings of this study emphasize the significance of aligning teaching methods with the unique demands of various academic writing genres. Academic writing is not merely a tool for academic achievement but a vital skill for professional communication and problem-solving in diverse fields. The integration of tailored instructional strategies, such as process-based, genre-based, and task-based approaches, can enhance students' proficiency and adaptability in writing. For instance, scaffolding and explicit instruction provide step-by-step guidance for novice writers, while reflective practice and content-based instruction promote independent thinking and discipline-specific skills.

The proposed framework highlights the importance of using model texts, collaborative activities, and digital tools to address challenges in academic writing. By linking writing instruction to real-world contexts, educators can foster student engagement and practical application of skills. This holistic approach not only prepares students for academic success but also equips them with lifelong competencies for professional growth. Future research should explore the long-term impact of these pedagogical methods on students' academic and career trajectories, further refining the teaching of academic writing across disciplines.

REFERENCES

1. Badger, R., & White, G. (2000). A process genre approach to teaching writing. *ELT Journal*, 54(2), 153-160. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/54.2.153>
2. Bazerman, C. (2004). *The languages of disciplines: A study in the rhetoric of science*. Routledge.
3. Biber, D., Conrad, S., & Leech, G. (2002). *Longman student grammar of spoken and written English*. Pearson Education.
4. Brinton, D. M., Snow, M. A., & Wesche, M. (1989). *Content-based second language instruction*. Newbury House.
5. Ergashev, R., & Sayfiddinov, J. (2024). Theoretical foundations of learning and language teaching approaches. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 4(1), 75-84.
6. Ferris, D. R., & Hedgcock, J. S. (2014). *Teaching L2 composition: Purpose, process, and practice* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
7. Fink, A. (2013). *Conducting research literature reviews: From the internet to paper*. Sage Publications.
8. Graham, S., & Perin, D. (2007). Writing next: Effective strategies to improve writing of adolescents in middle and high schools. *A Report to Carnegie Corporation of New York*. Washington, DC: Alliance for Excellent Education.
9. Hyland, K. (2004). *Genre and second language writing*. University of Michigan Press.
10. Hyland, K. (2006). *English for academic purposes: An advanced resource book*. Routledge.
11. Johns, A. M. (1997). *Text, role, and context: Developing academic literacies*. Cambridge University Press.

12. Lea, M. R., & Street, B. V. (1998). Student writing in higher education: An academic literacies approach. *Studies in Higher Education*, 23(2), 157-172. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079812331380364>
13. Lockhart, C. (2000). *Collaborative writing: Technique, relationships, and learning*. Longman.
14. Maftuna, Y., & Sohib, E. R. (2024). ANALYZING TASK-BASED WRITING APPROACHES: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVES AND PRACTICES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 4(02), 66-81.
15. Murray, R., & Moore, S. (2006). *The handbook of academic writing: A fresh approach*. Open University Press.
16. Nation, I. S. P. (2001). *Learning vocabulary in another language*. Cambridge University Press.
17. Paltridge, B., & Starfield, S. (2007). *Thesis and dissertation writing in a second language: A handbook for supervisors*. Routledge.
18. Pajares, F. (2003). Self-efficacy beliefs, motivation, and achievement in writing: A review of the literature. *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, 19(2), 139-158. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10573560308222>
19. Pecorari, D. (2013). *Academic writing and plagiarism: A linguistic analysis*. Bloomsbury.
20. Russell, D., Lea, M., Parker, J., Street, B., & Donahue, T. (2009). Exploring notions of genre in “academic literacies” and “writing across the curriculum”: Approaches across countries and contexts. In L. Björk et al. (Eds.), *Writing in Context(s): Textual Practices and Learning Processes in Sociocultural Settings* (pp. 395-423). John Benjamins.
21. Schön, D. A. (1983). *The reflective practitioner: How professionals think in action*. Basic Books.
22. Swales, J. M. (1990). *Genre analysis: English in academic and research settings*. Cambridge University Press.
23. Swales, J. M., & Feak, C. B. (2012). *Academic writing for graduate students: Essential tasks and skills* (3rd ed.). University of Michigan Press.
24. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
25. Weissberg, R., & Buker, S. (1990). *Writing up research: Experimental research report writing for students of English*. Prentice Hall.
26. Willis, J. (1996). *A framework for task-based learning*. Longman.